

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
TOURISM (BASED ON THE RESEARCH OF SCIENTISTS)

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Abstract. *In this article, tourism, its role in economic development, the importance of social media in the development of tourism, and the researches of foreign scientists in this regard are analyzed. Most domestic researchers believe that building communities on the Internet is the goal of any social network that unites people depending on their interests and related activities, and, accordingly, social networks are the basic and fundamental characteristics of social media.*

Keywords. *Tourism, economy, economic development, social media, Internet, social network, media marketing, interactive media.*

In the context of the active development of the information space and telecommunication technologies, new terms, concepts and designations appear both in everyday life and in the scientific literature. Today, close attention of specialists in various fields is paid to such a concept as “social media” - a concept that does not have an unambiguous definition and understanding by both foreign and domestic scientists and researchers in this field of activity.

Social media is part of interactive media, one of the communication channels for both individual users (individuals) and entire corporations and companies (legal entities). It is worth noting that often concepts such as “social media” and “social networks” are used as synonyms, identifying and replacing each other. The same can be said for social media marketing and social media.

But social media marketing is a broader concept than social media marketing. If we talk in general about points of view on social media, then the opposing views of domestic and foreign authors are clearly visible. Thus, domestic scientists and specialists often equate the concept of “social media” with the concept of “social networks,” which is not entirely accurate. Most domestic researchers believe that building communities on the Internet is the goal of any social network that unites people depending on their interests and related activities, and, accordingly, social networks are the basic and fundamental characteristics of social media. In practice, the nature of social media is simplified, thereby limiting its prospects and capabilities.

More often, concepts are substituted: within the same work, “social media” and “social networks” can be used as synonyms.

Foreign understanding of social media is based on theory associated with new technologies. So Paul Gillen gives the following definition of social media: “a polysemantic term that combines various online technologies that allow users to communicate and interact with each other.”

According to this author, social media users are the distinctive feature of the media. Professors of the Graduate School of Commerce (ESCP Europe) M. Haenlein and A.M. Kaplan defines social media as “a steadily growing and evolving collection of online tools, platforms and applications that allow us all to interact and share information.” Social media also means “any Internet service that allows users to unite in communities of interest, communicate with each other, publish their own content and exchange it.”

Social media is an interactive way of transmitting information, a channel and a means of communication, where the main subjects are the users themselves, who not only generate and exchange content, but also create close social connections.

As noted by L.P. Shesterkin, “social media have become a full-fledged social institution of modern society, and their main characteristics are accessible interactive communications; direct participation of users in the generation and retransmission of media content; high degree of user involvement in the process of interactive communication; maximum speed of feedback between users; user personalization.”

The authors made an attempt to determine the significance of social media as a tool for promoting tourism products and services in the hospitality and tourism market. Presentation of the main research material. Social media refers to a new type of online media, where any Internet user can become a participant in the process of creating, storing and disseminating information to the general public. Social media creates an interactive environment in which users interact with each other, building various types of communications to exchange information, and imply two-way communication between users who have the opportunity to create their own media content.

Social media is an effective tool for building communications between different groups of consumers and users who are similar in certain characteristics, needs and interests. From a business point of view, social media is the optimal tool in the context of integration and globalization, helping to promote business and create loyal customers at low cost.

Most often, social media includes: social networks (for example, MySpace, Facebook, Odnoklassniki.ru, VKontakte, LinkedIn), blogs (for example, Blogger, LiveJournal) and microblogs (for example, Twitter), forums, review sites (to for example, Irecommend.ru, Otzyv.ru), photo hosting (for example, Picasa, Flickr) and video hosting (for example, YouTube) and others. All social media have certain properties that determine their features and specificity. First of all, this is interactivity, as the possibility of communication between users and the exchange of various kinds of content, which is the basis of the development of the

information society and an indicator characterizing the speed of communication between one user and another.

In addition, social media has the properties of communication, mobility, accessibility, and versatility. A special place in the list of innovative tools for promoting tourism products and services is occupied by SMM marketing, which is based on the use of various types of social media. “No one doubts anymore that using the power of social media and social networks to promote destinations is an effective and promising strategy.”

Social Media Marketing (SMM) can be interpreted as the most promising way to promote goods and services using instant messaging services, the blogosphere, social networks and forums, that is, all social media channels available today. day.

SMM is a powerful and effective tool for managing a company’s reputation, building consumer loyalty to brands and solving other business development problems. “SMM is considered as a set of various measures that promotes companies, solutions, business tasks, and so on with the help of social media involved in this process.”

The essence of SMM is to form public opinion for the purpose of commercial success in promoting a tourism product by building communication links with target audiences. In practice, the popularity and effectiveness of SMM marketing are associated with the benefits that social media provides.

“Social media has created an excellent technical and emotional opportunity to maintain relationships with potential tourists, maintaining a sufficient level of trust between them. Social media makes it possible to build, on the basis of the experience presented online, “a fragment of a collective tourist picture of the world,” which allows a potential tourist to present an image, a “portrait” of a destination, the decision to visit which a person is ready to make, based on the reviews and comments of people who have already been there.” . If we talk in

general about the use of social media in promoting tourism products, then it is social media that allows a tour company to manage the opinions and recommendations of the target audience, form groups of loyal consumers, increase brand awareness, increase sales and implement targeted advertising.

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